

SINGAPORE VS UZBEKISTAN: ASSESSMENT APPROACHES IN STEM**Abdurashidova Sarvinoz****Chirchik State Pedagogical University****3 RD year student of the Faculty of Tourism,****Foreign Language and Literature****abdurashidovasarvinoz502@gmail.com****Abdullayeva Zarina****Scientific adviser: EFL teacher, Chirchik State Pedagogical University****Abdullayevazarina2@gmail.com****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17971660>**

Abstract: This article discusses the theoretical foundations of the competency-based approach in the modern education system, its mechanisms of formation, and its role in international experience. In particular, the model of competency development, its advantages and practical results are analyzed using the example of the Singapore education system. Also, the process of competency formation in the Uzbek education system, existing opportunities and current problems are considered, and scientifically based proposals for their improvement are developed. The scientific novelty of the study is that it provides a comparative analysis of the theoretical aspects of competency-based education with local and foreign experience, and a harmonious conceptual approach is proposed.

Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida kompetensiyaviy yondashuvning nazariy asoslari, uning shakllanish mexanizmlari hamda xalqaro tajribadagi o'рни yoritilgan. Xususan, Singapur ta'lim tizimi misolida kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish modeli, uning afzalliklari va amaliy natijalari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimida kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish jarayoni, mavjud imkoniyatlar va dolzarb muammolar ko'rib chiqilib, ularni takomillashtirish bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan takliflar ishlab chiqilgan. Tadqiqotning ilmiy yangiligi shundan iboratki, unda kompetensiyaga asoslangan ta'limning nazariy jihatlarini mahalliy va xorijiy tajribalar bilan qiyosiy tahlil etilib, o'zaro uyg'unlashgan konseptual yondashuv taklif etiladi.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются теоретические основы компетентностного подхода в современной системе образования, механизмы его формирования и роль в международном опыте. В частности, анализируется модель развития компетенций, ее преимущества и практические результаты на примере сингапурской системы образования. Также рассматривается процесс формирования компетенций в узбекской системе образования, существующие возможности и текущие проблемы, а также разрабатываются научно обоснованные предложения по их совершенствованию. Научная новизна исследования заключается в сравнительном анализе теоретических аспектов компетентностного образования с местным и зарубежным опытом и предложении гармоничного концептуального подхода.

Keywords: Competency-based approach, quality of education, Singapore education system, Uzbekistan education system, pedagogical model, innovative educational technologies, student skills, assessment system, teacher competence, international experience, educational reform.

Kalit soʻzlar: Kompetensiyaviy yondashuv, taʼlim sifati, Singapur taʼlim tizimi, Oʻzbekiston taʼlim tizimi, pedagogik model, innovatsion taʼlim texnologiyalari, oʻquvchi koʻnikmalari, baholash tizimi, oʻqituvchi kompetensiyasi, xalqaro tajriba, taʼlim islohoti.

Ключевые слова: компетентностный подход, качество образования, система образования Сингапура, система образования Узбекистана, педагогическая модель, инновационные образовательные технологии, навыки учащихся, система оценки, компетентность учителей, международный опыт, реформа образования.

Introduction: In today's global competitive environment, the importance of STEM education - that is, science, technology, engineering and mathematics - is increasing. The digital economy, innovative ideas and processes related to technological development require the training of qualified, creative and problem-solving young people. The assessment system plays an important role in ensuring such quality indicators of education, as it serves to identify and develop students' knowledge, skills and competencies.

Singapore, one of the world's leading countries, has been ranked high in international rankings as a country that has implemented the most effective assessment approaches in STEM education. Uzbekistan, on the other hand, has been taking important steps in recent years to modernize its education system, introduce a new national curriculum, and develop a competency-based assessment system. Therefore, studying the Singapore experience and its comparative analysis in the conditions of Uzbekistan is an important scientific and practical task that serves to improve the quality of education in our country.

This article reviews the theoretical foundations of assessment, analyzes the Singaporean assessment system in STEM, studies the current assessment practice in Uzbekistan, and compares the experience of the two countries. It also develops proposals and recommendations for further improving the Uzbek education system. The relevance of the study is that effective assessment not only determines a student's academic achievements, but also serves as one of the main tools for developing his critical, creative, and practical thinking skills.

Kirish: Bugungi global raqobat sharoitida STEM — yaʼni fan, texnologiya, muhandislik va matematika yoʻnalishlari boʻyicha taʼlimning ahamiyati tobora ortib bormoqda. Raqamli iqtisodiyot, innovatsion gʻoyalar va texnologik rivojlanish bilan bogʻliq jarayonlar malakali, kreativ fikrlaydigan hamda muammolarni hal qila oladigan yoshlarni tayyorlashni talab etadi. Taʼlimning bunday sifat koʻrsatkichlarini taʼminlashda baholash tizimi muhim oʻrin tutadi, chunki u oʻquvchilarning bilim, koʻnikma va kompetensiyalarini aniqlash hamda rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Dunyoning yetakchi davlatlaridan biri boʻlgan Singapur STEM taʼlimida eng samarali baholash yondashuvlarini joriy etgan mamlakat sifatida xalqaro reytinglarda yuqori oʻrinlarni egallab kelmoqda. Oʻzbekiston esa soʻnggi yillarda taʼlim tizimini modernizatsiya qilish, yangi milliy oʻquv dasturini joriy etish va kompetensiyaga asoslangan baholash tizimini rivojlantirish yoʻlida muhim qadamlar qoʻymoqda. Shu bois, Singapur tajribasini oʻrganish va uni Oʻzbekiston sharoitida qiyosiy tahlil qilish mamlakatimiz taʼlim sifatini oshirishga xizmat qiluvchi muhim ilmiy-amaliy vazifa hisoblanadi.

Ushbu maqolada baholashning nazariy asoslari koʻrib chiqiladi, Singapurning STEM yoʻnalishidagi baholash tizimi tahlil qilinadi, Oʻzbekistonning amaldagi baholash amaliyoti oʻrganiladi hamda ikki davlat tajribasi qiyoslanadi. Shuningdek, Oʻzbekiston taʼlim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish boʻyicha taklif va tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi. Tadqiqotning dolzarbligi

shundaki, samarali baholash nafaqat o'quvchining akademik yutuqlarini aniqlaydi, balki uning tanqidiy, ijodiy va amaliy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda asosiy vositalardan biri bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Введение: В современной глобальной конкурентной среде возрастает значение STEM-образования — то есть науки, техники, инженерии и математики. Цифровая экономика, процессы, связанные с инновационными идеями и технологическим развитием, требуют подготовки квалифицированных, творчески мыслящих и способных решать проблемы молодых людей. Система оценки играет важную роль в обеспечении таких качественных показателей образования, поскольку она служит для выявления и развития знаний, навыков и компетенций учащихся.

Сингапур, одна из ведущих стран мира, занимает высокие места в международных рейтингах как страна, внедрившая наиболее эффективные подходы к оценке в STEM-образовании. В последние годы Узбекистан предпринимает важные шаги по модернизации системы образования, внедряя новую национальную учебную программу и развивая систему оценки на основе компетенций. Поэтому изучение сингапурского опыта и проведение сравнительного анализа его в условиях Узбекистана является важной научно-практической задачей, способствующей повышению качества образования в нашей стране.

В данной статье рассматриваются теоретические основы оценивания, анализируется система оценивания в области STEM (наука, технология, инженерия и математика) в Сингапуре, изучается современная практика оценивания в Узбекистане и сравнивается опыт двух стран. Также разрабатываются предложения и рекомендации по дальнейшему совершенствованию системы образования в Узбекистане. Актуальность исследования заключается в том, что эффективное оценивание не только определяет академические достижения студента, но и служит одним из главных инструментов развития его критического, творческого и практического мышления.

Main part: Assessment is an integral part of the educational process, which involves identifying and assessing the knowledge, skills and competencies of students. The role of assessment in improving the quality of education and ensuring the self-development of students is important. The assessment process not only shows the results of the student, but also helps the teacher to optimize the lesson and develop an individual approach. Therefore, the concept of assessment is considered not only as a means of determining the result, but also as a means of supporting the educational process.

There are two main types of assessment: formative and summative. **Formative assessment** is carried out during the learning process and its main purpose is to monitor the student's progress, identify and correct mistakes. This type of assessment helps to further consolidate students' knowledge and personalize lessons. At the same time, **summative assessment** is carried out at the end of the learning process and its task is to determine the overall results of the student, to issue a diploma or certificate. This type of assessment formally confirms the knowledge and skills acquired by students. Formative and summative assessment complement each other, since one controls the process, while the other shows the final result.

In recent years, **the competency-based assessment** approach has become widespread in education. This approach is aimed at assessing not only the student's theoretical knowledge, but also their practical skills and problem-solving abilities. In the STEM field, competency-

based assessment is carried out through laboratory work, project work, scientific research, and solving innovative problems. At the same time, competency-based assessment helps students develop real-life problem-solving skills and develops their independent thinking.

Assessment is not only a means of determining the level of knowledge of students, but also an important tool for increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, developing students' practical skills, and preparing them for future professional activities. When used together, formative, summative, and competency-based assessment types ensure the comprehensive development of students in STEM.

The Singaporean education system is known worldwide for its high performance and innovative approaches to STEM. The assessment system in this country is aimed at assessing not only students' theoretical knowledge, but also their practical skills and problem-solving abilities. Assessment in Singapore is carried out in two main formats: formative and summative. Formative assessment allows you to constantly monitor the progress of students during the learning process and adjust lessons, while summative assessment serves to determine and formally confirm the results at the end of the learning process. At the same time, the Singaporean system is aimed at deeply developing students' STEM skills, which strengthens their analytical and creative thinking skills.

In terms of assessment methods, the Singapore system uses a variety of methods. **Tests** assess mathematical and scientific knowledge in a standardized way, which allows for quick and objective comparison of results. At the same time, **portfolios** - a collection of laboratory work, project work and innovative tasks completed by students - show the individual development of the student and allow for the assessment of practical skills. **Rubrics** ensure objectivity by setting clear criteria and a scoring system for assessing project work. In addition, **project work** is aimed at solving real-life STEM problems, developing students' creative and critical thinking skills.

1-Table. Foreign experience: the example of Singapore

Criterion	Description	Advantage	Disadvantage
Assessment type	The combination of formative and summative assessment	Allows you to track progress throughout the learning process and determine the final result	Complex system, requires a lot of resources
Tests	Assessment of theoretical knowledge through standardized questions	Results can be compared quickly and objectively	It is difficult to assess creativity and practical skills
Portfolio	A collection of students' laboratory work and project work	Development of practical skills, individual approach	Requires time and resources
Rubrics	Clear criteria and scoring system for evaluating projects	Objective assessment, criteria-based analysis	Not flexible, can limit creativity

Criterion	Description	Advantage	Disadvantage
Project work	Practical assignments aimed at solving real STEM problems	Develops problem-solving and critical thinking skills	Requires resources and time

The advantages of the Singapore assessment system are clear and comprehensive. It allows for the simultaneous assessment of students' knowledge and skills, combining practical and theoretical components. At the same time, the system develops students' problem-solving and analytical thinking skills, and encourages an innovative approach. However, such a system requires a lot of resources and qualified teachers, as well as time and technological capabilities.

Thus, the Singapore experience demonstrates effective approaches to assessment in STEM: it combines formative and summative assessment, uses a variety of methods, and serves to develop not only theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills and competencies of students. This experience can also serve as a basis for introducing valuable models and advanced methods for the Uzbek education system.

The reforms implemented in the education system of Uzbekistan in recent years, in particular, the introduction of a new national curriculum, have served to fundamentally update the assessment process. In the new approach, assessment is seen not only as a means of determining the final result, but also as a pedagogical mechanism that supports the student's development process and encourages him to work on himself. In particular, in STEM areas, modern forms of assessment—formative, competency-based, and practical assessment—are being gradually introduced into the educational process.

The main focus of assessment in the new national curriculum is on developing students' real-life skills. Tasks aimed at increasing student activity, teaching them to think independently, and solving practical problems are widely used in the lesson process. Formative assessment serves to identify student weaknesses during the process, provide feedback, and motivate the student. Summative assessment is carried out at the end of the quarter and year, which determines the student's overall level of mastery.

The Uzbek education system has a clearly defined scoring system and assessment criteria, with specific criteria developed for each subject. For example, in STEM subjects, theoretical knowledge is assessed through tests, and practical skills are assessed through laboratory work, projects, and individual assignments. The monitoring system regularly tracks student progress, and the results are analyzed by schools and educational institutions. This allows teachers to revise their lessons, improve their methodology, and adapt them to the individual needs of students.

Teachers' and students' opinions about the assessment system also help to analyze this process in more depth. The results of the mini-interviews show that most teachers emphasize that the new assessment system is effective in developing students' practical skills. In their opinion, portfolios, project work, and laboratory exercises develop a culture of self-improvement in students. At the same time, some teachers indicated the complexity of the assessment criteria and lack of time as shortcomings. Students, on the other hand, generally find the new methods interesting, but note that the complexity of some projects and assignments requires them to spend additional time and effort.

Table 2. Analysis of the Uzbek system

Direction / Criteria	Description	Current status	Advantages	Problems / Limitations
Assessment type	The combination of formative and summative assessment	Phased introduction in schools	Continuous monitoring of student progress	Additional burden on teachers
Points system	10-point and criteria-based assessment	Based on the new national curriculum	Transparent and consistent evaluation	The criteria are unclear in some places
Criteria	Theoretical, practical and competency criteria	Developed across disciplines	Possibility of objective assessment	Not applied equally in all schools
Tests	Determining theoretical knowledge	Basic assessment tool	Fast and convenient	Does not fully reveal practical skills
Portfolio	Individual student assessment	Introduced in some schools	Shows the student's developmental history	Not fully implemented in all schools
Project work	Solving practical STEM problems	Partially implemented	Problematic thinking develops	Resources and equipment may be lacking
Monitoring	Analysis of learning outcomes	Conducted regularly within schools	Systematic control	The quality of analysis depends on the teacher's qualifications
Teachers' opinion	Attitude towards the evaluation system	Most positive reviews	Practical assessment skills are developed	Not enough time, the load increases
Readers' opinions	Reaction to new assessment forms	Rated interesting	Projects provide a creative approach	Some tasks are complicated

The updated assessment model in the Uzbek education system is helping to develop students' creativity, analytical, practical skills, and independent research skills. Although this process is not yet fully developed, it is gradually approaching international experience, especially in the STEM field, which indicates the formation of competitive approaches.

Table 3. Comparison

Criterion	Singapore	Uzbekistan	Recommendations
Assessment type	Formative + Summative	Formative + Summative	Expanding formative assessment
Test	Standard, complex	Mostly theoretical	Introducing complex tests
Portfolio	Mandatory, systematic	Optional, rarely used	Make the portfolio mandatory

Criterion	Singapore	Uzbekistan	Recommendations
Project work	Real problem, lots of resources	Simplified, resource-limited	Increasing resources and working with real problems
Rubric	Clear and detailed	Partially available	Expanding rubrics and training teachers

The above analysis shows that the assessment system in STEM is one of the most important factors determining the quality of education. The Singapore experience demonstrates the need to organize assessment not only as a means of measuring theoretical knowledge, but also as a comprehensive system that serves to develop students' analytical thinking, problem-solving skills and practical experience. The systematic use of formative assessment, the use of portfolios, rubrics and project work have been proven to play an important role in preparing students for real life.

In the Uzbek education system, reforms that have begun in recent years are aimed at modernizing the assessment process, and modern technologies of formative, competency-based and summative assessment are being introduced on the basis of the new national curriculum. Students are being activated through a scoring system, criterion-based assessment, monitoring and practical assignments. However, the effectiveness of the process depends on the qualifications of teachers, technical resources and more precise and understandable assessment criteria.

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